

**DAILY LAND SURFACE TEMPERATURE FROM MULTIPLE EARTH OBSERVATION
DATA FUSION**

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ABSTRACT

Land surface temperature (LST) is one of the most important variables for the terrestrial ecosystem. [1] It stands as a fundamental Essential Climate Variable (ECV) [2] and hold paramount significance across different environmental and agricultural domains [3].

Temperature estimation from satellites is increasingly widespread, which allows to obtain large-scale and almost real-time informations.

However, estimating temperature using satellite data has some limitations: presence of cloud cover has an impact on remotely sensed observations [4].

This paper presents a data fusion approach for enhancing Sentinel-3 LST products by replacing cloudy pixels with data from MODIS, GCOM-C and ERA5-Land. The model has been tested on a trial study area, but its versatility allows it to be applied worldwide.

The resulting fused LST product is subjected to an evaluation against LANDSAT 8 and 9 LST data. The performance of the data fusion demonstrates the efficacy of the proposed fusion method, with Pearson correlation values ranging from 0.60 to 0.93.

The study not only contributes to advancements in LST data quality but also establishes a benchmark for future research in satellite data fusion.

1. INTRODUCTION

LST is one of the most important parameters in the physical of land surface process [5]. It reflects the interplay of energy and water exchange between the land surface and the atmosphere. This exchange significantly impacts vegetation growth and shapes patterns of land use and land cover [6,7,8,9].

Remote sensing stands as an indispensable tool in the estimation of LST; LST computation from satellite data is widely used widely used for climate change or urban heat effect studies [10], for drought monitoring [11] as well as evotranspiration estimation [12].

GCOM-C SGLI Level 3 provides 1-day, 8-day and 1month temporal resolution products of global land surface temperature with 1/24 deg as spatial resolution.

ERA5-Land gives a hourly land surface temperature simulation dataset with a spatial resolution of 0,1°x0,1°; ERA5-Land data are validated against multiple in-situ observations as well as by satellite-based global reference dataset [13].

The spatial coverage and resolution afforded by remote sensing platforms, whether satellites or airborne sensors, enable a comprehensive observation of LST variations at different scales – from urban microclimates to extensive geographic regions. This capacity is particularly vital for discerning patterns and changes in LST over time.

In the realm of environmental and urban climate studies, the quest for accurate LST estimation is marked by inherent challenges within individual satellite datasets. These challenges, notably the persistent presence of cloudy pixels, temporal gaps and variable spatial resolutions, underscore the limitations that can impede the precision of LST products. It is against this backdrop that our motivation to adopt a data fusion methodology which can be applied worldwide emerges.

Traditional satellites often grapple with compromised data quality due to cloud cover. The presence of cloudy pixels introduces uncertainties into LST estimates. To address this challenge, our scope lies in using alternative sources; these datasets, with their distinct characteristic, act as complements during periods of cloud cover, thereby enhancing the overall robustness of the LST product. Given the significant variation of Land Surface

Temperature throughout both day and night, to ensure temporal coherence among all the data used, a one-hour filter from the starting reference data has been applied.

2. DATA

The reference product used is SLSTR Level-2 LST Sentinel-3, which has a daily temporal resolution and 1 km measurement grid. The Sea and Land Surface Temperature Radiometer (SLSTR) is on board Sentinel-3A and Sentinel3B satellites.

This study makes use of data from MODIS, GCOM-C and ERA5 to replace Sentinel-3 cloudy pixels.

MODIS Land Surface Temperature/Emissivity Daily (MOD11A1) Version 6.1 product provides daily per-pixel Land Surface Temperature and Emissivity (LST&E) with 1 kilometer (km) spatial resolution in a 1,200 by 1,200 km grid.

The outcome of the combined LST product undergoes an assessment to the LANDSAT 8 and 9 LST data. An overview of the data used is illustrated in table 2.1.

Satellite	Original product name	Native format	Spatial resolution
Sentinel-3	S3A_SL_2_LST S3B_SL_2_LST	NetCDF	1 km

MODIS	MOD11A1	HDF	1 km
GCOM-C	GC1SG1	H5	1/24°
ERA5-Land	ERA5-Land skin temperature	CSV	0,1°
Landsat 8/9	LC08_L2SP_ LC09_L2SP_	GeoTIFF	30m

Tab.2.1 - Overview of the land surface temperature products

3.METHODOLOGY

3.1. Test case area

We have tested our model within the Po Basin, a comprehensive region spanning multiple northern Italian territories. This basin encompasses Liguria, Piemonte, Valle d'Aosta, Emilia-Romagna, Toscana, Lombardia, Provincia Autonoma di Trento, Marche, and Veneto regions (see Fig 3.1.1). This testing approach allows us to demonstrate the applicability and replicability of our methodology on a larger scale.

Fig.3.1.1 - Hydrographic Po Basin Area

3.2. Data fusion step

The initial step employs a time filter, allowing a maximum time difference of one hour. This ensures temporal coherence, capturing concurrent LST conditions across the selected satellites. It is not certain that, for a given observation day, all products are available for data fusion.

The products have the following native formats: netCDF for Sentinel 3, hdf for MODIS, h5 for GCOM-C and csv for ERA 5 Land: to have a common format to be able to work together all the data were converted in tiff format; the datasets are then reprojected to the WGS 84 coordinate system, promoting homogeneity in spatial representation.

The conversion from digital number to LST values in Celsius degrees follows the reprojection step, ensuring uniformity in temperature measurements across all datasets.

Different cloud masks are applied based on the characteristics of each satellite product.

For Sentinel 3 data the LST variable datafile contains LST that has not been cloud cleared. A cloud-free LST product was obtained by referring to the documentation relating to the flags_in.nc datafile, present in the downloaded data.

For MODIS and GCOM-C products a cloud mask is applied referring to the cloud flag present within the data.

ERA5-Land dataset does not include a cloud mask being a simulated product. For ERA5-Land, which has an elevate spatial resolution, a resampling process is introduced to align its resolution with that of Sentinel-3. This adjustment is essential to harmonize the datasets and facilitate a seamless integration in subsequent fusion steps.

Subsequently, a cropping process is executed using a shapefile corresponding to the area of interest: in this phase all available temperature products are in Celsius degrees in tiff format, re-projected in WGS84 with cloud cover mask applied and cropped only on the area of interest.

The heart of our data fusion methodology lies in the replacement of Sentinel-3's cloudy pixels with valid pixels from other satellites. This process is done with a specific order of priority: MODIS, GCOM-C, and ERA5. MODIS, owing to its original similar spatial resolution to Sentinel- 3, provides more detailed temperature data than other products; GCOM-C has worse spatial resolution and it is used when MODIS data is not sufficient to replace all Sentinel-3 cloudy pixels and ERA5, utilized as a last product due to its simulation nature, fills gaps when no other valid data is available.

Fig.3.2.1 - Algorithm's scheme

The algorithm's scheme is shown in Figure 3.2.1 while an example of a data fusion map, dated June 13, 2021, is shown in Figure 3.2.2.

Fig.3.2.2 - Example of data fusion map

To validate the accuracy and reliability of our obtained results, a comparison was conducted with LST values derived from Landsat 8 and 9 satellites. This evaluation adhered to a maximum time difference of one hour from Sentinel-3 data, ensuring temporal coherence between the datasets. The Landsat data, renowned for its high spatial resolution (30 metres) and long-term observational consistency, served as a robust benchmark for assessing the precision of our fused Land Surface Temperature product.

The validation procedure also includes the application of a cloud mask which is provided by the Pixel Quality Assessment Band (QA_PIXEL). The cloud-masked Landsat data was then cropped using the same shapefile employed for the data fusion, ensuring consistency in the study area.

Subsequently, a digital number to LST conversion was performed on the Landsat data. Landsat data have a spatial resolution of 30 meters, and this posed a challenge in direct comparison due to the lower spatial resolution of our data fusion map at 1 km. To address this, a resampling procedure

was implemented on Landsat data, increasing its pixel size from 30 to 300 meters.

To bridge the spatial gap between the higher-resolution Landsat data and the coarser-resolution data fusion product, for every Landsat resampled pixel within a distance less than half the size of a Sentinel 3 pixel, a mean value was computed. While this approach precludes a one-to-one comparison due to the inherent spatial differences between the two datasets, it enables a meaningful synthesis of information.

Subsequently, the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE), the Pearson correlation and the Relative Root Mean Square Error rRMSE were calculated between the Land Surface Temperature values derived from the data fusion product and the corresponding mean values obtained from the Landsat dataset.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The scatterplot map between data fusion product and Landsat data, with the RMSE and Pearson coefficient values, is represented in Figure 4.1.

Fig.4.1 - Example of scatterplot

On the x-axis there are the Celsius degrees temperature value of the data fusion map, on the y-axis the average value of the landsat pixels.

The scatterplot considers only data fusion non-cloudy pixels, which can be directly compared with Landsat data; for

cloudy pixels ERA5 data was used, which is an already validated product [13].

The data fusion process yielded compelling outcomes, showcasing a robust agreement between the Land Surface Temperature values derived from our fusion product and the benchmark Landsat dataset. The Pearson correlation coefficient, a measure of the linear relationship between the two datasets, stood impressively high at 0.93. This strong positive correlation signifies a substantial alignment in the variations and trends observed in the LST values.

Furthermore, the RMSE, a metric quantifying the average magnitude of the differences between corresponding values, was found to be 2.63.

In addition to the Pearson correlation coefficient (0.93) and RMSE value (2.63), the evaluation of the rRMSE further accentuates the performance of the methodology. The calculated rRMSE, with a value of 0.07, underscores the precision and robustness of the fused LST values.

The rRMSE provides a normalized measure of the RMSE, considering the magnitude of errors relative to the range of observed values. The low rRMSE value indicates that the discrepancies between the fused LST values and the Landsat benchmark are minimal in proportion to the overall variability in the dataset. To comprehensively assess the performance and robustness of our data fusion methodology, simulations were conducted across all the 2021, aimed to capture the variability in LST estimation under different climatic conditions, providing insights into the methodology's adaptability to diverse environmental contexts.

The results from these seasonal simulations revealed a consistent and promising trend in the performance of the data fusion approach. Across the majority of the datasets, the Pearson correlation coefficient consistently exceeded 0.6. This high correlation persisted across various seasonal dynamics, underlining the methodology's ability to maintain accuracy across different climatic conditions. Furthermore, the Relative Root Mean Square Error (rRMSE) consistently remained below 0.25.

5. CONCLUSION

Our study introduces a data fusion methodology aimed at enhancing the completeness of LST estimations, particularly using Sentinel-3 satellite data. The proposed approach involves replacing cloudy pixels in Sentinel-3 LST products with complementary data from MODIS, GCOM-C, and ERA5, ensuring temporal coherence with a maximum time difference of one hour. The evaluation of the fused LST product against Landsat 8 and 9 datasets showcased compelling results. A high Pearson correlation coefficient, low RMSE and rRMSE value collectively affirm the robustness and accuracy of data fusion methodology. Seasonal analyses further demonstrated the adaptability of our methodology across different climatic conditions. While

slight variations were observed during the winter season, the methodology's overall reliability remained evident.

The versatility of our model allows for its application worldwide, underscoring its potential impact on a global scale.

Our research contributes furthermore to advancing the field of LST estimation, addressing challenges associated with cloud cover. As satellite technology continues to evolve, the methodologies introduced in this study provide a valuable framework for harnessing the full potential of diverse satellite datasets in enhancing our understanding of surface dynamics.

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